

Sedition vis-vis Right to Speech

A debate over the provisions related to freedom of speech is always ignited in India whenever any proceeding has been initiated against any speech given by any person. Either it is a matter of Kanhaiya Kumar of Jawaharlal Nehru University, or of Hardik Patel of Gujarat, or of Separatists of Kashmir. In all such matters, a debate is always burned up over the concept of Sedition vs. Freedom of Speech, and it is appearing that such debates will be continued in the future also.

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Introduction :

The Supreme Court of India and the High Courts of the states are also involved in the debate which was re-ignited in the entire country after the incidence of Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi. This debate of Sedition vs. Freedom of Speech and Expression is not of a new origin, but it was in continued existence from British Reign.

In 1870, Section 124-A was added in the Indian Penal Code 1860, and in 1898 drastic amendments has been made in this provision by the British rulers. After Independence, this provision was again amended with the object to make it favourable for sovereign India by inserting the word 'Government of India' in place of 'Dominion of India'. The basic concept involve in Section 124-A of IPC was not Sedition, rather it was exciting a disaffection. The first caselaw related to the Section 124-A of IPC was Queen-Empress vs Jogendra Chunder Bose And Ors. (1892) ILR 19 Cal 35.⁽¹⁾ And after the amendment in the provision the first landmark judgement was Queen Empress vs. Bal Gangadhar Tilak (1897 ILR 22 Bombay 112)⁽²⁾. It was held in this case that for constituting an offence of sedition under Section 124-A, it is not essential that a person should commit riots or rebellion or any kind of disturbance to the peace. Insulting the Government or generating hatred for the Government amongst the people is sufficient to constitute an offence of sedition.

Till this judgement, neither we were having any constitution of our own nor we were assured with any kind of fundamental rights. India got its independence in 1947 and our constitution was drafted by the Constituent Assembly on 26th November 1949 and it was came into force

on 26th January 1950. Our Constitution guaranteed 7 Fundamental Rights to us which are presently 6 in number. The Right to Property has been repealed from the Part III of the Indian Constitution through Constitutional (44th Amendment) Act 1978 and hence it is no longer remained a Fundamental Right. Out of 6 Fundamental Rights, the Right to Freedom is the most significant fundamental right which has been ensured from Article 19 to Article 22 of the Indian Constitution. Amongst these Fundamental Freedoms, Article 19(1)(a) guarantees the freedom of speech and expression to each and every citizen of India.

However, the freedom of speech and expression guaranteed under Article 19(1)(a) is not an absolute right. Article 19(2) provides certain grounds on the basis of which State can impose certain reasonable restrictions over the fundamental freedom guaranteed under Article 19(1)(a). These grounds are :

- (1) Sovereignty and Integrity of India,
- (2) Security of State,
- (3) Decency or Morality,
- (4) Contempt of Court,
- (5) Defamation,
- (6) friendly relations with foreign States,
- (7) public order and
- (8) incitement to an offence.⁽³⁾

Initially there only 5 ground were there for restriction, Later on, through Constitutional (First Amendment) Act 1951, three more grounds of reasonable restrictions has been added in Article 19(2), which are -

- (1) Public Order,
- (2) Friendly relations with foreign states, and

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(3) Incitement for offences.

No doubt, these grounds of reasonable restrictions has been incorporated in the Indian Constitution by the Constituent Assembly with a thought that if guaranteed absolutely than this right might be misused by the people. Hence, they had imposed restrictions over freedom of speech and expression of the citizens through the grounds given in Article 19(2).

Now, let us discuss the Delhi incidence of Jawaharlal Nehru University. On 9th February 2016, an event of reciting the poems was organized in the JNU campus with the approval of University Administration on the topic of "A country without post office". But eventually it ended with the sloganeering by the students which was considered as offensive and because of this the Police authorities of Basant Kunj Police Station arrested the Kanahaiya Kumar and his friends on the charges under Sections 124-A/ 120-B/ 34/ 147/ 149 of Indian Penal Code, and the matter is under investigation at present. This incidence has again ignited a debate over Section 124-A of Indian Penal Code vs. Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution.

According to Section 124-A of the Indian Penal Code "Whoever, by words, either spoken or written, or by signs, or by visible representation, or otherwise, brings or attempts to bring into hatred or contempt, or excites or attempts to excite disaffection towards, the Government established by law in India shall be punished with imprisonment for life, to which fine may be added, or with imprisonment which may extend to three years, to which fine may be added, or with fine.

Explanation 1 : The expression "disaffection" includes disloyalty and all feelings of enmity.

Explanation 2 : Comments expressing disapprobation of the measures of the Government with a view to obtain their alteration by lawful means, without exciting or attempting to excite hatred, contempt or disaffection, do not constitute an offence under this section.

Explanation 3 : Comments expressing disapprobation of the administrative or other action of the Government without exciting or attempting to excite hatred, contempt or disaffection, do not constitute an offence under this section.

If we examine the this provision then we find that in the case of BILALAHMED KALOO V/S STATE OF ANDHRA PRADESH , decided on Wednesday, August 6, 1997, it is said that the offence of sedition under section 124A is the doing of certain acts which would bring the Government established by law in India into hatred or contempt, or create disaffection against it. If we talk the important ingredient of section 124-A, we can say that-

- (1) There should be bringing or attempting to bring into hatred or contempt or exciting or attempting to excite disaffection towards the Government of India. And
- (2) Such act of attempt may be done-
 - (a) By words, either spoken or written, or
 - (b) By signs, or

(c) By visible representation.

On the combine interpretation of the Article 19(1)(a) along with the restrictions given in Article 19(2), it is clear that sedition is also a reasonable ground of restriction over the freedom of speech and expression.

After coming into force of Indian Constitution the validity of this section was considered by Supreme Court in the case of Ramesh Thapar⁽⁴⁾ and Brijbhushan⁽⁵⁾. As a result of these two decisions Constitution first amendment Act was passed in 1951. Thereafter in Kedar Nath Singh case the validity of this section was again questioned on the ground of the provisions of this section being in violation of freedom of speech and expression. The was negated by the court and the section was held to be constitutional. The explanation to the section makes it clear that criticism of public measures or comment on Government action, however strongly worded, within reasonable limits and consistent with the fundamental right of freedom of speech and expression is not affected. It is only when the words have the pernicious tendency or intention of creating public disorder or disturbance of law and order that the provisions of the section are attracted.

Any act within the meaning of section 124-A which has the effect of subverting the Government by bringing that government into contempt or hatred or creating disaffection against it would be within penal statute because the feeling of disloyalty to the government established by law or enmity to it imports the idea of tendency to public disorder by the use actual violence or incitement to offence.

In other words, any written or spoken words. etc. which has implicit in them the idea of subverting government by violent means which are compendiously included within the term 'revolution' have been made penal by the section in question.⁽⁶⁾

In Shreya Singhal vs. Union of India⁽⁷⁾, hon'ble Supreme Court issue following three principles to test the freedom of speech and expression:

- (1) Debate.
- (2) Advocacy.
- (3) Incitement.

Debate and Advocacy are the soul of Article 19(1)(a) but as soon as any of these enters into the definition of incitement, it falls in the domain of Article 19(2) and so can't avail the fundamental right guaranteed under Article 19(1)(a).

I am not getting this when we claim our fundamental freedom guaranteed in Indian Constitution, why do we not respect the fundamental duties whereas both are provided by same Constitution. Part IV A of the Indian Constitution provides following 11 Fundamental Duties for each and every Indian citizen under Article 51A:

- (a) to abide by the Constitution and respect its ideals and institutions, the national Flag and the National Anthem;
- (b) to cherish and follow the noble ideals which inspired our national struggle for freedom;
- (c) to uphold and protect the sovereignty, unity and integrity of India;

(d) to defend the country and render national service when called upon to do so;

(e) to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities; to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women;

(f) to value and preserve the rich heritage of our composite culture;

(g) to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life, and to have compassion for living creatures;

(h) to develop the scientific temper, humanism and the spirit of inquiry and reform;

(i) to safeguard public property and to abjure violence;

(j) to strive towards excellence in all spheres of individual and collective activity so that the nation constantly rises to higher levels of endeavor and achievement.

(k) who is a parent or guardian to provide opportunities for education to his child or, as the case may be, ward between the age of six and fourteen years.

Conclusion :

Thus it is clear from the above discussion that Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution guarantees the freedom of speech and expression alongwith certain reasonable restrictions given in Article 19(2). Out of the various grounds given in Article 19(2), this freedom can be restricted on the ground of unity and integrity of the nation, which includes the offence of sedition in it as it is defined in Section 124-A of IPC. Hence, it can be concluded that freedom of speech and expression is not an absolute right and reasonable restrictions can be imposed on it. Further, We must also understand that the constitution is not a common book. Each of his words should be more than every religion book.

If our constitution is giving us some basic rights then it is also imposing some basic duties on us and is expecting something from us and it is our duty to fulfil this demand of the Constitution otherwise we have no right to demand the fundamental rights.

References :

- (1) <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/334102/>
- (2) <https://indiankanoon.org/docfragment/1188602/?formInput=queen%20empress%20v.%20bal%20gangadhar%20tilak>
- (3) <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1218090/>
- (4) AIR 1950 SC 124.
- (5) AIR 1950 SC 129.
- (6) Prof. Mishra S.N. INDIAN PENAL CODE, 288, (7th ed.) 2009.
- (7) (2015)5 SCC 1.

The screenshot shows the UGC Approved List of Journals website. The header reads 'UGC - APPROVED - JOURNAL'. The page title is 'UGC Approved List of Journals'. A search bar shows 'Research Link' and 'Total Journals : 1'. A table lists the journal details:

View	Sl.No.	Journal No.	Title	Publisher	ISSN	E-ISSN
View	1	4896	Research Link	Research Link	09731628	

Below the table, there are sections for 'For Students', 'For Faculty', and 'More' with various links and information.

The screenshot shows the 'UGC Journal Details' page for 'Research Link'. The details are as follows:

Name of the Journal :	Research Link
ISSN Number :	09731628
e-ISSN Number :	
Source :	UNIV
Subject :	Accounting, Anthropology, Business and International Management, Economics, Econometrics and Finance (all), Education, Environmental Science (all), Finance, Geography, Planning and Development, Law, Political Science a, Social Sciences (all)
Publisher :	Research Link
Country of Publication :	India
Broad Subject Category :	Arts & Humanities; Multidisciplinary; Social Science

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